

IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT ON YOUTH EMPLOYMENT IN ABUJA

ASHOGBON ESTHER OLUYINKA¹ and OLAJIDE OLADIPO²

^{1,2}Department of Economics, Nile University of Nigeria.

Abstract

This study examines the impact of entrepreneurship development on youth employment in Abuja. Data were collected from young entrepreneurs within Abuja and complemented by secondary sources to provide a comprehensive analysis of the socio-economic challenges and opportunities within Nigeria's labour market. To evaluate the impact of these interventions, the research employs statistical models, including logit regression analysis, to test hypotheses around the correlation between entrepreneurship training programs and youth employment growth. Findings reveal that investment in targeted entrepreneurship training correlates positively with employment and economic activity, with youth participants displaying higher job readiness and innovation capabilities. The study underscores the need for strategic policy frameworks that promote technical education, support sustainable enterprise development, and encourage public-private partnerships. In conclusion, the research advocates for enhanced governmental and institutional investment in entrepreneurship development as a means of reducing youth unemployment and fostering economic resilience in Abuja and beyond. The insights provided aim to guide policymakers, educators, and development practitioners toward implementing sustainable solutions that harness entrepreneurship as a cornerstone of economic empowerment for Nigerian youth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Innovation, Youth Training, Youth Unemployment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is the creation or extraction of economic value. It is the act of being an entrepreneur, or the owner or manager of a business enterprise who by risk and initiative, attempts to make profits (Parker, 2022). Entrepreneurs act as managers and oversee the launch and growth of an enterprise. An entrepreneur is an individual who owns, organizes and manages a business and in so doing, assumes the risk of either making profit or losing the investment. It is seen as the privileged road to enhance the creation of new jobs and increase GDP (Parker, 2022). Entrepreneurship development plays a crucial role in fostering economic growth and reducing unemployment, particularly among youth populations. In Abuja, Nigeria's capital, youth unemployment remains a significant socio-economic challenge despite various governmental and non-governmental interventions. The promotion of entrepreneurship as a means of job creation has gained traction as an effective solution to this issue. The growing rate of youth unemployment in Abuja poses a significant economic and social challenge, leading to increased poverty, crime, and social unrest. Despite various efforts to promote job creation, traditional employment avenues have not been sufficient to absorb the large number of young job seekers. This has highlighted the need for alternative strategies, such as entrepreneurship, to create sustainable employment opportunities.

Entrepreneurship development offers young people the potential to become job creators rather than job seekers. However, many aspiring entrepreneurs face challenges such as inadequate funding, lack of business mentorship, and an unfavorable business environment. By conducting

this study, we aim to analyze the effectiveness of entrepreneurship programs in Abuja, identify key obstacles young entrepreneurs encounter, and propose solutions to enhance their success.

Oni (2022) notes that the high unemployment incidence of secondary school leavers is a reflection of improper coordination of the educational system. Lambo (2018) criticises the government expenditure policy, in which most government projects (industries and public utilities) in Nigeria have been cavernous, cutting across all age groups, educational strata, and geographical entities. One particular feature of the unemployment problem in Nigeria is that it was more endemic in the early 1980s. This is clearly evident in the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2010). For instance, the unemployment rate rose from 4.3 percent in 1976 to 6.4 percent in 1980. Although there was some marginal decline between 1981 and 1986, the rates were relatively higher than what is obtained in the national unemployment rate of 3.0 percent. The unemployment rate declined progressively from 7.0 percent in 1987 to 1.8 percent in 1995 and thereafter increased gradually to 3.4 percent in 1996. The rate remained unchanged at 3.2 percent in 1997 and 1998 but fell to 3.0 percent in 1999. Beginning in 2000, the unemployment rate in Nigeria registered double digits. However, the rate declined from 9.1 percent in 2000 to 12.2 percent in 2002, increased to 14.8 percent in the succeeding year, and then declined by 3.0 percentage points to 11.8 percent in 2004. However, in 2005 it increased to 11.9 percent and subsequently 16.1 percent in 2010, as at 2016 it further rose to 20% (NPC, 2017).

The federal government recently acknowledged that about 80 percent of Nigeria's youth is unemployed, and 10 percent underemployed (Daily Trust, November 26, 2008) others have urged the youth to become "entrepreneurs" and reject "social vices" (Thisday, March 17, 2009). At some point the former minister of Education, Dr. Sam Egwu, has expressed concern about the poor quality of graduates from the nation's educational institutions. The political leaders are good at cataloguing the revisions for Nigeria's problems and predicting the future without implementing reasoned policies to create a better future. However, as the management guru, Peter Drucker, has observed that; if you want to predict the future, create it" (as cited in Wilson and Blumenthal, 2018:1). It is good enough to implore the youth to become productive citizens and "entrepreneurs" or to reject "social vices" without providing them with skills and resources. One major aspect of development is provision of employment opportunities for citizenry. The figures also reveal that urban unemployment rate were stable at 8 to 10 percent from 1991-1995; declined to 4-6 percent between 1990 to 17 percent in 2003, and then sharply declined to 10.1 percent in 2005. The rural rate followed the urban pattern from 1991 to 1998; rose sharply in 1999 and, since then, stated a gradual decline which culminated in 12.6 percent in 2015. This shows that labour underutilization is a common phenomenon, especially in rural areas. Another form of labour underutilization in Nigeria is underemployment. Available data for underemployment in both rural and urban areas of Nigeria for 2012 and 2018 for which data were available from National Bureau of statistics (NBS, 2019). A careful study of the data shows that the underemployment rate of each year in the rural areas far exceeds that in urban areas. In most of the years, specifically 2012, 2015 and 2018, the average rural underemployment rates doubled those of urban averages. The trend from 2012 to 2018 shows that underemployment problems is a significant problem in Nigeria. Underutilization normally assumes the form of disguised employment, which is very difficult to measure. In addition, a

breakdown of unemployment rates by states, age, and educational attainment is presented to enable us to appreciate the specific problems of the labour market.

Furthermore, the higher rate of unemployment in rural areas contributes significantly to increased poverty levels compared to urban areas, as highlighted by recent data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) indicating that 67.1% of Nigerians live below the poverty line. Seasonal human resource wastage is a concerning phenomenon, particularly when considering that over 59% of the employed labor force operates in rural areas (Lambo, 2022). The growing proportion of unemployed youths compounds the challenge, with variations observed across locations (urban/rural) and education levels.

The historical trajectory, as outlined by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), underscores the evolving nature of unemployment rates. The transition from urban to rural unemployment rates in the early 2000s is a notable shift, signifying the changing dynamics. The latest statistics from NBS in 2023 indicate a staggering unemployment rate of 33.30%, with factors such as an increasing number of graduates, a freeze on employment in various sectors, and slow government budget disbursement contributing to this rise. The growing rate of youth unemployment in Abuja poses a significant economic and social challenge, leading to increased poverty, crime, and social unrest. Despite various efforts to promote job creation, traditional employment avenues have not been sufficient in absorbing the large number of young job seekers. This has highlighted the need for alternative strategies, such as entrepreneurship, to create sustainable employment opportunities. Entrepreneurship development offers young people the potential to become job creators rather than job seekers. However, many aspiring entrepreneurs face challenges such as inadequate funding, lack of business mentorship, and an unfavorable business environment. By conducting this study, we aim to analyze the effectiveness of entrepreneurship programs in Abuja, identify key obstacles young entrepreneurs encounter, and propose solutions to enhance their success.

This research is particularly important as it will provide empirical evidence on how entrepreneurship development can contribute to youth employment. The findings will serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, development agencies, and stakeholders in designing more effective entrepreneurship support programs. Ultimately, this study seeks to promote economic empowerment, reduce youth unemployment, and foster long-term economic growth in Abuja. The main objective of the study is to examine the impact and significance of entrepreneurship development factors on youth employment rate in Abuja, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses are stated as follow:

- H₀₁: Youth empowerment programme is not significantly related to youth employment rate in Abuja.
- H₀₂: Youth training does not significantly incite youth employment rate in Abuja.
- H₀₃: Technical and vocational education does not significantly correlate with youth employment rate in Abuja.

H₀₄: Innovation rate is not significantly related to youth employment rate.

H₀₅: Youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate do not jointly exert youth employment rate.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship Development

Entrepreneurship Development is defined as a process of enhancing the skillset and knowledge of entrepreneurs regarding the development, management and organization of a business venture while keeping in mind the risks associated with it (UNESCO & ILO, 2022). This is carried out through training programs and sessions which are aimed at accentuating entrepreneurial acumen. Pursuing this field as a career, you will be working towards facilitating skill development amongst budding entrepreneurs and assisting them to tackle their struggles with building their businesses (UNESCO & ILO, 2022). Entrepreneurship development is the process of enhancing entrepreneurial knowledge and skills via structured training programme. It deals with the study of entrepreneurial behaviour, dynamics of business, and its development and expansion. The objectives of entrepreneurship development programme are to increase the knowledge and skill of existing entrepreneurs and encourage others to become one. Ultimately, it helps in increasing the number of such individuals in an economy (UNESCO & ILO, 2022).

Employment

Employment is defined as an act or instance of employing someone or something, or the state of being employed (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Employment is defined as any employment or combination of one or more employments in which an individual works the full standard work week prescribed by the governing body or earns the full rate assigned to the position (World Bank, 2018). Youth Employment efforts aim to address youth unemployment by improving business environments, enhancing educational and vocational training, and promoting entrepreneurship and equal opportunities (Okigbo, 2019). Youth unemployment is a significant global issue affecting economic stability and development, with young women often facing greater challenges (Okigbo, 2019).

Theoretical Review

This study is underpinned by the Innovative Entrepreneurship /Schumpeter's Notion of Entrepreneurship Schumpeter's notion of entrepreneurship and economic development is simply that an entrepreneur is an innovator. Schumpeter's characterization of capitalism is directly based on the roles the entrepreneur plays within it and he rejected outright the market as being a perfectly competitive construct. He views the market as a dynamic process driven by creative skills which he associates with "new combination" and thus, economic development and progress. He contends that the entrepreneur is the prime innovator. In addition to being an innovator, the entrepreneur is also a leader. His actions channel the means of production into previously unexploited market and other producer follow him into these new markets.

Empirical Review

Gambo et al. (2025) examines how the growth of entrepreneurship affects the generation of employment opportunities in Nasarawa State. Even though entrepreneurship is crucial for generating employment, there are still obstacles in the way of its growth. These include limited support from governmental and non-governmental organizations, difficulty obtaining financing and microcredit, proper training and enlightenment etc. The objective of this paper is to investigate how the growth of entrepreneurship affects the creation of jobs in Lafia, Nasarawa State. The study used a descriptive research design, and the means used for gathering data was a questionnaire given to new entrepreneurs in Lafia, Nasarawa State. A sample size of 375 was determined from a population of 1604 using a Smith (1984) sampling formula; this sample represented the number of questionnaires that were delivered. This findings of the research demonstrated that the creation of jobs in Nasarawa State is significantly impacted by the growth of entrepreneurship. This implies that through entrepreneurship development, self-reliance and employment opportunities have been created in Lafia, Nasarawa State. Through this, youths have been able to develop a way to create value in the society. More so, this study revealed that access to credit (micro credit) has a significant effect on employment creation in the State. Having acquired knowledge on how to manage finance they make sound financial decisions. Lastly, the study showed that the number of new businesses established has a significant effect on employment creation in Nasarawa State. This result implies that youths who apply their entrepreneurship skills and creativity in one nature of business or the other have been able to earn a living out of it in Nasarawa State.

Balogun and Marafa (2022) investigate the effects of entrepreneurship development on employment generation in some selected rural areas of Kebbi state, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study population consists of 4122 participants (rural dwellers) in eighteen (18) local government areas of Kebbi state. Research advisor (2006) was used to determine 357 participants. The study used purposive, deliberate and simple random sampling techniques and a self-designed questionnaire. The study concluded that entrepreneurship development is a source of employment generation for rural dwellers in Kebbi state. The study further recommended that there is need for Kebbi state government to intensify efforts to expand capacity of entrepreneurship development program to continue generating employment for rural dwellers through adequate funding for sustainability.

Adebayo, (2022), examines the effect of the self-employment programme of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) on youth unemployment in Nigeria. The study traced youth unemployment to diverse but mutually reinforcing factors, such as rapid population growth, rapid expansion of the education system, improper design of educational system to match education with employment opportunities rural-urban migration, the nature of production technique, government concretionary economic policies of the past and the existence of barriers to smooth inter-regional and inter-state movement in search of employment opportunities within the Nigerian labour market. Also, the study's review of NDE programme showed that as much as the employment scheme of the agency are relevant, there is a limit to which they can be relied upon as a lasting solution to Nigeria's unemployment problem. The study,

therefore, recommended the restructuring of the Nigerian educational system to lay emphasis on self-employment and self-reliance. It equally recommended that the employment schemes of the NDE be pursued with stronger commitment in terms of finance and physical activities.

Alabi and Salami (2022) examines various factors associated with entrepreneurship development. The sample size of 395 was derived using Taro Yamane Statistical Formula. The study employed cluster sampling in the selection of respondents as 350 questionnaires were administered and 45 respondents interviewed. The quantitative data (obtained through questionnaire) was analyzed using simple statistical percentages while the qualitative data (derived from interview) was analyzed in narrative and descriptive form. Beside chi-square, contingency was used to determine significant test. The research findings demonstrated that skills development whether domestic, business, agriculture, technical and computer will facilitate job creation though, negative displacement factors like unemployment, job insecurity, etc tend to encourage entrepreneurship. On the other hand, the study further revealed that lack of fund, entrepreneurial skill, policy inconsistency, inadequate infrastructure, innovative ideas and risk are factors preventing entrepreneurship. The study proffers recommendations that entrepreneurial trainings should be provided by experienced entrepreneur or qualified consultants to provide expertise knowledge and mentorship, development of skills should be encouraged as skill acquisition centres is developed in all twelve (12) political wards in AMAC for easy accessibility. AMAC and Ministry of Federal Capital Territory (MFCT) should collaborate with Bank of Industry (BOI) to provide credit facilities to interested graduates to enhance more participation in entrepreneurship and government should embark on infrastructure development to reduce unit cost of production in AMAC, particularly in satellite communities.

Bonito et al. (2017) researched on work titled; “Do entrepreneurship and economic growth affect poverty, income inequality and economic development? Their main objective is to examine the impact of entrepreneurship and economic growth on poverty, income inequality and economic development. The study used regional data obtained from observation from the official government document in the Philippines.

Using regression on cross sectional data and applying Hausman test to choose between effect and Random Effect which examine the magnitude and the effects of each explanatory variable to the dependent variables. The result suggested that economic growth plays a vital role on poverty, income inequality and economic development; entrepreneurship has impact on economic development but has little or no impact on poverty and income inequality in the Philippines.

The result of their work agrees with the expected result of this study. However, there is no recommendation by the authors based on the study conducted. Nevertheless, it was expected that in the North Central region of Nigeria through entrepreneurship, unequal income distribution would be mitigated as such social services are distributed equally across each community, thereby benefiting each individual in the local and urban region of the country and this may be readily achievable through private sector.

Musa et al. (2016) researched on politics of poverty programs in Nigeria: challenges and prospects. The objective of the paper was to examine the politics of poverty alleviation before, and after the implementation of the structural adjustment program in Nigeria. The researchers adopted the use of contextual analysis. The result found out that fifty poverty alleviation programme were inaugurated but poverty in Nigeria has not abated; political insecurity, inadequate policy continuity, corruption, mismanagement of resources allocated for the programs, social evil such as terrorism, insurgencies, communal and inter-religious conflicts were crippling the poverty reduction programme. The study recommended good agricultural policies and agribusiness initiatives, provision of social amenities, revival of War Against Corruption, institutionalization of vocational education and training centers and entrepreneurship innovations to serve as a noble solution to the pitiful situation in Nigerian economy.

Haider (2017) examined the sectoral analysis of employment demand (jobless growth) in Pakistan. He employed an augmented employment demand equation in which employment was expressed as a function of output (GDP) under a pooled data analysis for the period 1974-2008 with estimations of threshold level of economic growth for seven (7) sectors of Pakistan economy with OLS estimation method. The results obtained by Haider (2017) indicated that jobless growth exists only in the manufacturing sector of the Pakistan economy and that sector required a high threshold level of economic growth. Lending credence to the study of Khemraj et. al., (2016) for the United States' case; Mate (2010) undertook a theoretical and growth accounting approach of jobless growth. He analysed data on OECD countries and concludes that the link between labour and output has changed. More so, Sahar (2011) enunciated tackling the paradox of (national) jobless growth in Jordan. He used OLS method and observed an inverse relation between FDI and unemployment, on the one hand, and GDP growth and unemployment, on the other hand. He concludes that while conventional economic reforms brought some economic stability, they did not reduce national employment and that the peculiarities of labour market and structural features of the economy affect macroeconomic policy than the other way around.

Nonetheless, the study of Swane and Vistrand (2016) took a descriptive study on jobless growth in Sweden examined the relationship between employment and GDP and selected macroeconomic variables and also made a cross-sectional comparison. They developed two models on the basis of Okun's law and their results showed that employment elasticity with respect to GDP was about 0.7 percent for Sweden and does not change much over time. The relationship between employment and GDP was found to be strongly positive and this, together with the relatively constant employment elasticity over time, suggested that the previous situation in Sweden was due to temporary discrepancy and not fundamental change in the relationship. More so, Ingham and Ingham's (2018) extrapolated the jobless growth in Poland. In their study, it was observed that Poland's post-communist economic performance has been generally good but for many years, its growth was jobless; it exhibited very high unemployment rates and concomitantly made little progress in approaching the targets set for European Union member states under the Lisbon strategy.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts survey research design This study focuses on impact of entrepreneurship development on youth employment rate in Nigeria, with Abuja the FCT as study area. Abuja is the capital and seat of Administrative power and eighth most populous city of Nigeria. Situated in the middle of the country within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Data for this work is of the primary source which were collected with the use of structured and open-ended Questionnaires. Questionnaires will be used to gather information from the relevant stakeholders. The researcher used area sampling where the total area “Abuja” was divided into a few local governments and then into settlements within those local government areas as geographical clusters. The choice of area sampling was because the researcher does not have the list of the population concerned. The population for this study comprises both registered and non-registered MSMEs operating within Abuja metropolis. Thus, the population of the study is 482,365 comprising male and female entrepreneurs in Abuja.

Sample size for this study was determined using Yamane formula (Yamane, 1967). The use of Yamane formula for sample size determination is because the area councils in Abuja is known or finite. According to him sample size from a finite population is obtained using,

$$n_o = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad \text{(Yamane, 1967)} \quad \text{---(1)}$$

Where,

n_o = Sample size from the population

N = Total population

e = Margin of error assumed at 5%

The population of $N = 482,365$ and $e = 0.05$.

Therefore, $n_o = \frac{482365}{1+482365(0.05)^2} = 399.66858 \approx 400$ respondents.

Therefore, the researcher elicits information from 400 respondents in some local government areas across Abuja based on purposive selection to capture diversity. These encompass Abuja Municipal, Kuje, Bwari, Abaji, Gwagwalada.

Table 1: Summary of the study population

Respondents	Stratum population
Youth empowerment	154,195
Youth training	105,646
Technical and vocational education	128,234
Innovation rate	94,290
Total	482,365

Source: NARPPN, 2022

Thus, sample per local government area shall be determine as:

$$nN = \frac{n_i}{\sum n_i} (n_o) \quad \text{---(2)}$$

Where,

nN = sample size per local government

n_i = population per local government

n_o = Total sample size

$\sum n_i$ = Total sum of population per local government

Table 2: Sample Per Stratum Across Categories of beneficiaries in Abuja

Respondents	n_i	n_o	nN
Youth empowerment	154,195	400	128
Youth training	105,646	400	88
Technical and vocational education	128,234	400	106
Innovation rate	94,290	400	78
Total	482,365		400

Source: CAC, 2024

The sample comprises 128 Youth empowerment, 88 Youth training, 106 Technical and vocational education, and 78 Innovation rate. The sample was distributed among the selected council as in the table below.

Table 3: Sample Distribution in Five Selected Local Government Areas in Abuja

Respondents	LGAs within Abuja					Total
	Abuja Municipal	Kuje	Bwari	Abaji	Gwagwalada	
Youth empowerment	54	38	14	15	7	128
Youth training	39	26	10	8	5	88
Technical and vocational education	31	22	24	16	13	106
Innovation rate	26	15	11	12	14	78
Total	150	101	59	51	39	400

Source: Researchers computation (2025)

Measurement and Coding of Variables

The research used Nominal scale of Measurement and Coding of Variables where 0 is assigned to people who are Employed and 1 to those Unemployed. Also, YEMP – Youth empowerment (1 if empowered; 0 if not), Ytrain – Youth training (1 If trained by the government; 0 if not), TVedu – Technical and vocational education (1 = if yes; 0 if no), InR – Innovation rate (1= if there is innovation; 0 if not).

Model Specification

To substantiate the investigation's focus, crucial macroeconomic variables and indicators are incorporated into the model.

The analytical framework employs a logit regression model represented as:

$$\text{Log YER} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log YEMP} + \beta_2 \text{Log YTRN} + \beta_3 \text{Log TVED} + \beta_4 \text{Log INOR} + \mu \quad (3)$$

Where:

YER=Youth employment rate

YEMP = Youth empowerment programe

YTRN = Youth training

TVED = Technical and vocational education

INOR = Innovation rate

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and β_4 = Partial slopes of the regression model

μ = Stochastic error term.

This model structure enables a comprehensive exploration of the relationship between entrepreneurship development and youth employment rates in Nigeria. The incorporation of government expenditures and innovation rates ensures a nuanced understanding of the dynamics influencing youth employment in Nigeria. The model's coefficients (β_1 to β_4) provide insights into the individual impact of each variable, while the stochastic error term (μ) accounts for unobserved factors affecting the youth employment rate. This rigorous model specification forms the foundation for a robust analysis of the research hypotheses and contributes to a nuanced understanding of the intricate relationships within the context of entrepreneurship development and youth employment in Nigeria.

Logit Regression Model

Logistic regression analyzes the relationship between multiple independent variables and a categorical dependent variable and estimates the probability of occurrence of an event by fitting data to a logistic curve. Logit regression is actually a nonlinear regression (Kim et al., 2018). The essence of computing Logit involves understanding statistical procedures; odds, probability and log odds. Odds is the ratio between something happening to something not happening ($p / 1-p$) and probability is the ratio of something happening (event occurs) to everything that could happen (occurs).

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Before estimating the Logit model, descriptive statistics of the characteristics of the respondents and respondents' perception of entrepreneurship development and youth employment was first presented regarding the percentage count of the responses to have an overview of the responses. Moreover, this is important as it provides an overview of respondents' responses.

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Selected Local Government Areas in Abuja

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Abaji	48	12.3	12.3	12.3
	Abuja Municipal	147	37.8	37.8	50.1
	Bwari	57	14.7	14.7	64.8
	Gwagwalada	38	9.8	9.8	74.6
	Kuje	99	25.4	25.4	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 5 shows the frequency distribution of selected Local Government Areas in Abuja. A total of 400 questionnaires were administered in the study area. 150 questionnaires were distributed to respondents in Abuja Municipal, 147 (37.8%) questionnaires were filled and returned. A total of 101 questionnaires were distributed to respondents in Kuje, 99 (25.4%) questionnaires were filled and returned. 59 questionnaires were distributed to respondents in Bwari local council, 57 (14.7%) questionnaires were filled and returned. 51 questionnaires were administered to respondents in Abaji, 48 (12.3%) questionnaires were filled and returned. 39 questionnaires were distributed to respondents in Gwagwalada, 38 (9.8%) questionnaires were filled and returned. Not all the questionnaires administered were retrieved. This is because questionnaires were not administered to the respondents and retrieved on spot. This has paved way for laxity on response to the questionnaires on the part of respondents.

Descriptive Statistics of Respondent’s Demographic Characteristics

The study presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents to determine their potentials, responsibility, and capability. Thus, the characteristics that affect the above intent were analyzed and they are shown as thus.

Table 5: Sex of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	307	78.9	78.9	78.9
	Female	82	21.1	21.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	0

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 5 shows the sex of the respondents. The highest percentage of 78.9 percent (307) of respondents were male while 21.1 percent (82) were female. This result is in consonant with Misango and Ongiti (2013), which asserted that, Nigeria women, especially those in the local and regional areas, though have physical ability for work such as farm work and small entrepreneurship businesses, are yet to have equal entrepreneurial opportunities with their male counterparts. This could be as the result of hindrances from customary beliefs of the people such as women seclusion is in the area.

Table 6: Age of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	104	26.7	26.7	26.7
	31-40	160	41.1	41.1	67.9
	41-50	98	25.2	25.2	93.1
	Above 50	27	6.9	6.9	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 6 shows the age of the respondents. The age status of the respondents was taken for the purpose of understanding the age bracket of the respondents in the study area. The result on age of the respondents shows that, the highest percentage of respondents 41.1% (160) are within the age group of 31 - 40, and 26.7 % (104) are within the age group of 20 - 30. Those within the age group of 41 – 50 are about 25.2% (98), and those within the age group of 51 and above are 6.9% (27) of the total number of respondents. Therefore, the youth among the respondent are 67.8% (264) when put together. This result implies that, there is a high entrepreneurial potential in the region. The economic cost of this is increase of entrepreneurship output and regeneration of the entrepreneur’s capital.

Table 7: Marital Status of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	287	73.8	73.8	73.8
	Married	87	22.4	22.4	96.1
	Divorced	15	3.9	3.9	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The marital status and the number of children of respondents taken were for the purpose of determining the level of the entrepreneurs’ responsibilities. Table 4.4 shows that the married among the respondents are 22.4% (87), The singles among the respondents are 73.8% (287) Only 3.9% (15) of the respondents are divorced. This result shows that more than half or entrepreneurs (54%) are single; a low dependency ratio, which has no burden on their entrepreneurship business progress.

Table 8: Household Size of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-3	157	40.4	40.4	40.4
	4-6	108	27.8	27.8	68.1
	7-9	96	24.7	24.7	92.8
	9 and above	28	7.2	7.2	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 8 shows that the highest respondents of 40.4% (157) of the total respondent in the study area have a family size of 1-3 children, followed by 27.89% (108) respondent with 4-6 children.

24.7 % (96) of the respondents have 7-9 children and only 7.2% (28) of the respondents have more than 9 children.

Table 9: Educational Status of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Qur'anic Education	19	4.9	4.9	4.9
	Primary Education	37	9.5	9.5	14.4
	Secondary Education	111	28.5	28.5	42.9
	Post-Secondary Education	93	23.9	23.9	66.8
	First Degree	74	19.0	19.0	85.9
	Post Graduate Degree	55	14.1	14.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 9 shows the educational qualification of the respondents. The educational qualification status is to show the level of education attained by the respondents. Highest respondents of 28.5% (111) in the selected area are secondary school graduates, followed by 23.9% (93) respondents who have post-secondary education. 19.0% (74) respondents have first degree education. 14.1% (55) respondents have post graduate degree. 9.5% (37) respondents have primary education while only 4.9% (19) respondents have qur'anic education. The study shows that the entrepreneurs have one form of education and or the other. Therefore, they are enlightened and are highly capable of excelling in entrepreneurship businesses. The result is in line with assertions UBEC (2010) which said that more than 50% of average families in the selected states are educated and that education is taken in a high premium in the area.

Table 10: Religious Background of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Islam	113	29.0	29.0	29.0
	Christianity	241	62.0	62.0	91.0
	Traditional Worshiper	35	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 10 shows that the religious background of selected respondents. 29.0% (113) of the respondents are Muslims, 62.0% (241) are Christians while about 9.0% (35) are traditional worshippers.

Descriptive Statistics of Respondent's Socio-economic Characteristics

Table 11: Reason for Engaging in Entrepreneurship by Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	I have no formal job	195	50.1	50.1	50.1
	I love business	130	33.4	33.4	83.5
	To supplement my formal job	64	16.5	16.5	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 11 shows the reason why respondents engaged in entrepreneurship in Abuja. Highest respondents of 50.1% (195) in the selected area engaged in entrepreneurship because they had no formal business, followed by 33.4% (130) respondents who were engaged in entrepreneurship due to love for business. However, 16.5% (64) respondents engaged in entrepreneurship to supplement their formal job.

A negligible number of the respondent of 16.5% (64) said that they engaged in entrepreneurship to complement their jobs. This result confirms the assertion of Noteboom and Stem (2008), that most African engage in entrepreneurship not because they know what it is but because of lack of livelihood.

Ako (2018) confirmed this by asserting that entrepreneurship in Nigeria is mostly necessary entrepreneur and not growth entrepreneurs because of the problem of unemployment in the country.

Table 12: Business Ownership Status of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Personal	38	9.8	9.8	9.8
	Inherited	78	20.1	20.1	29.8
	On Loan/Hire Purchase	156	40.1	40.1	69.9
	Rented	117	30.1	30.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 12 shows business ownership status of the respondents. The Business ownership status shows the entrepreneurs' business ownership structure. Highest respondents of 30.1% (117) in the study area rented the business assets, followed by 40.1% (156) respondents who operates their assets on loan or hire purchase. 20.1% (78) respondents inherited their business assets, while 9.8% (38) respondents the business properties as their personal assets.

Table 13: Reasons for On-loan/Hire Purchase or Rented Business by Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No business set up fund	195	50.1	50.1	50.1
	Under mentorship	78	20.1	20.1	70.2
	Like to be an employee	116	29.8	29.8	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 13 shows the reasons why respondents are on-loan/hire purchase or rented business. Highest respondents of 50.1% (195) are on-loan/hire purchase or rented business because they have no business set up fund, followed by 20.1% (78) of the respondents because they are currently under mentorship. 29.8% (116) of the respondents in Abuja are on-loan/hire purchase or rented business because they like to be an employee.

Table 14: Years of Experience by Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2-6 years	197	50.6	50.6	50.6
	7-11 years	56	14.4	14.4	65.0
	13 and above years	136	35.0	35.0	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 14 shows years of experience by respondents. The experience status is to show the entrepreneurs' skill and capability. Highest respondents of 50.6% (197) have only 2-6 years of experience in the business, followed by 35.0% (136) respondents who have 13 and above years of experience in the business while 14.4% (56) respondents have 7-11 years of experience in the business.

Table 15: Income of Respondents Before Starting a Business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below N250001	159	40.9	40.9	40.9
	N250001 - N500000	190	48.8	48.8	89.7
	N500001 - N750000	32	8.2	8.2	97.9
	N750001 and above	8	2.1	2.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 15 shows the income of respondents before starting a business. Highest respondents of 48.8% (190) had income of N250,001-N500,000 before starting a business, followed by 40.9% (159) respondents who had income below N250,001 before starting a business. 8.2% (32) respondents had income between N500,001-N750,000 before starting a business while 2.1% (8) respondents had income of N750001 and above before starting a business.

Table 16: Respondents Start-up Capital

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below N50,001	112	28.8	28.8	28.8
	N50001- N75000	92	23.7	23.7	52.4
	N75001 - N100000	76	19.5	19.5	72.0
	N100001 – N125000	55	14.1	14.1	86.1
	N125001 - N150000	38	9.8	9.8	95.9
	N150001 and above	16	4.1	4.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 16 shows respondents start - up capital. Highest respondents of 28.8% (112) started business with below N50,001, followed by 23.7% (92) respondents started business with N50001- N75000, 19.5% (76) respondents started business with N75001 - N100000, 14.1% (55) respondents started business with N100001-N125000, 9.8% (38) respondents started business with N125001 - N150000, while 4.1% (16) respondents started business with N150001 and above.

Table 17: Income Generated on Daily Basis by Respondents Before the Business

Valid	< 3000	110	28.3	28.3	28.3
	3001 – 6000	90	23.1	23.1	51.4
	6001 – 9000	75	19.3	19.3	70.7
	9001 - 12000	54	13.9	13.9	84.6
	12001 – 15000	38	9.8	9.8	94.3
	15001 and above	22	5.7	5.7	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 17 shows income generated on daily basis by respondents. Highest respondents of 28.3% (110) generates less than N3000 on daily basis, followed by 23.1% (90) respondents who generates between N3001 and N6000 on daily basis. 19.3% (75) respondents generate N6001 – N9000 on daily basis. 13.9% (54) respondents generate N9001 - N12000, 9.8% (38) respondents generate N12001 – N15000 on daily basis while only 5.7% (22) respondents generate N15001 and above.

Table 18: The Worth of the Respondent’s Business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 50,000	90	23.1	23.1	23.1
	50001-75000	70	18.0	18.0	41.1
	75001 - 100000	57	14.7	14.7	55.8
	100001 - 125000	48	12.3	12.3	68.1
	125001 - 150000	59	15.2	15.2	83.3
	150001 and above	65	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 18 shows the worth of the respondent’s business. Highest respondents of 23.1% (90) of the respondents in Abuja, has a business worth N50,000, followed by 18.0% (70) respondents who have a business worth N50001-N75000, 14.7% (57) respondents have a business worth N75001 - N100000, 15.2% (59) respondents have a business worth N125001 – N150000, 12.3% (48) respondents have a business worth N100001 - N125, 000, 16.7% (65) respondents have a business worth N150, 001 and above.

Table 19: Number of Days an Entrepreneur Goes to Work in a Week

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	7 Days	10	2.6	2.6	91.0
	6 Days	199	51.2	51.2	51.2
	5 Days	74	19.0	19.0	70.2
	4 Days	26	6.7	6.7	76.9
	3 Days	45	11.6	11.6	88.4
	2 Days	35	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 19 shows the number of days an entrepreneur goes to work in a week as indicated by

respondents in Abuja. The highest respondents of 51.2% (199) go to work for 6 days in a week, followed by 19.0% (74) respondents who go to work for 5 days in a week, 6.7% (26) respondents go to work for 4 days in a week, 11.6% (45) respondents go to work for 3 days in a week, 2.6% (10) respondents go to work for 7 days in a week while only 9.0% (35) respondents go to work for 2 days in a week.

Table 20: Average Current Expenditure in a Day by Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	N5000	41	10.5	10.5	10.5
	N3000	84	21.6	21.6	32.1
	N4000	45	11.6	11.6	43.7
	N2000	110	28.3	28.3	72.0
	N6000	77	19.8	19.8	91.8
	N7000 And above	32	8.2	8.2	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 20 shows the average current expenditure in a day by respondents. The highest respondents of 28.3% (110) spend on average N2000 in a day followed by 21.6% (84) respondents who spend on average N3000 in a day, 19.8% (77) respondents spend on average N6000 in a day, 11.6% (45) respondents on average spend N4000 in a day, 10.5% (41) respondents spend on average N5000 in a day while only 8.2% (32) respondents on average spend N7000 and above in a day.

Descriptive Statistics of Respondent's Political Characteristics

Table 21: Level of Awareness of Government Youth empowerment programme by respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	82	21.1	21.1	21.1
	YES	307	78.9	78.9	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 21 shows level of awareness of government youth empowerment programme by respondents. The highest respondents of 78.9% (307) are aware of the government youth empowerment programme and have also benefited from it while 21.1% (82) respondents are not aware of the government youth empowerment programme and as such have not benefited from it.

Table 22: Level of Attendance of Government Youth training programme by respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	75	19.3	19.3	19.3
	YES	314	80.7	80.7	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 22 shows the level of attendance of government youth training programme by respondents. The highest respondents of 80.7% (314) attended government youth training programme while 19.3% (75) of the respondents did not attend government youth training programme.

Table 23: Level of Benefit from the Government Technical and Vocational Education Programme by Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	70	18.0	18.0	18.0
	YES	319	82.0	82.0	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 23 shows the level of benefit from the government technical and vocational education programme by respondents. The highest respondents of 82.0% (319) benefited from the government technical and vocational education programme while 18.0% (70) respondents have not benefited from the government technical and vocational education programme in Abuja.

Descriptive Statistics of Respondent's Productivity

Table 24: Number of Businesses Setup by Respondents Since Start-up of the Business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	< 3	377	96.9	96.9	100.0
	3 or more	12	3.1	3.1	3.1
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 24 shows the number of businesses setup by respondents since start-up of the business. The highest respondents of 96.9% (377) setup less than 3 businesses since start-up while only 3.1% (12) respondents setup 3 or more businesses since start-up.

Table 25: Problem in Setting up Business by the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES (Delay and high cost of registration)	199	51.2	51.2	51.2
	YES (High business permit and license cost)	40	10.3	10.3	61.4
	High legal and professional fees	58	14.9	14.9	76.3
	High interest rate especially for starters	41	10.5	10.5	86.9
	Property rights	51	13.1	13.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 25 shows the problem encountered while setting up business by the respondents. The highest respondents of 51.2% (199) identified delay and cost of registration as problem faced while setting up a business in Abuja follow by 14.9% (58) respondents who identified high legal and professional fees as problem faced while setting up a business in Abuja. 13.1% (51) respondents identified property rights as problem faced while setting up a business in Abuja. 10.5% (41) respondents identified high interest rate especially for starters as problem faced while setting up a business in Abuja while 10.3% (40) respondents identified high business permit and license cost as problem faced while setting up a business in Abuja.

Table 26: Attendance of Entrepreneurship Sanitization Programme by Respondents since Start-up of Business

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES (2)	156	40.1	40.1	40.1
	YES (3)	50	12.9	12.9	53.0
	YES (1)	183	47.0	47.0	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 26 shows the attendance of entrepreneurship sanitization programme by respondents since start-up of business. The highest respondents of 47.0% (183) are aware of the government entrepreneurship sanitization programme but have attended it only once, followed by 40.1% (156) respondents who are also aware of the government entrepreneurship sanitization programme and have attended it twice. 12.9% (50) are aware of the government entrepreneurship sanitization programme and have attended it thrice. The study shows that the entrepreneurs have one form of skill and or the other. Therefore, they are skilled and are highly capable of excelling in entrepreneurship businesses. The result is in line with assertions UBEC (2010) which said that more than 50% of average families in the selected states are educated and that education is taken in a high premium in the area.

Table 27: The Last Time Respondents Attended Entrepreneurship Sanitization Programme

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	4 years ago	156	40.1	40.1	40.1
	3 years ago	50	12.9	12.9	53.0
	2 years ago	183	47.0	47.0	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 27 shows the last time respondents attended entrepreneurship sanitization programme. The highest respondents of 47.0% (183) attended entrepreneurship sanitization programme for the last time in 2 years ago, followed by 40.1% (156) of the respondents who attended entrepreneurship sanitization programme for the last time in 4 years ago while 12.9% (50) of the respondents attended entrepreneurship sanitization programme in the last 3 years ago. This implies that entrepreneurship programs are not properly disseminated and has not adequately

affected the lives in the society. This result shows that those entrepreneurship programs are far from reach by the majority of the entrepreneurs.

The Major Challenges Encounter Last Time Respondents Attended Entrepreneurship Sanitization Programme

Figure 1: the major challenges encounter last time respondents attended entrepreneurship sanitization programme

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Figure 1 above shows the major challenges encounter last time respondents attended entrepreneurship sanitization programme. The highest respondents of 329 identified lack of backup programme as the major challenge encountered at skill acquisition centre in Abuja, followed by 284 who identified lack of instructors as the major challenge encountered at skill acquisition centre in Abuja, 283 respondents identified discontinuity of programme as the major challenge encountered at skill acquisition centre in Abuja, while 181 respondents identified lack of teaching aids as the major challenge encountered at skill acquisition centre in Abuja.

Table 28: Level of Respondent’s Encouragement Through Government Entrepreneurship Incentive Programme and Subsidies Ever Since Setup

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	114	29.3	29.3	29.3
	YES	275	70.7	70.7	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 28 shows the level of respondent’s encouragement through government entrepreneurship incentive programme and subsidies ever since set-up.

The highest respondents of 70.7% (275) have been encouraged through government entrepreneurship incentive programme and subsidies ever since setup while the remaining 29.3% (114) respondents have not been encouraged through government entrepreneurship incentive programme and subsidies ever since setup.

Table 29: Federal Government Facilitation for Respondents in Terms of Collection of Tools, Services and Knowledge

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES	181	46.5	46.5	46.5
	NO	208	53.5	53.5	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 29 shows the arrangement of Federal government facilitation for respondents in terms of collection of tools, services and knowledge.

The highest respondents of 53.5% (208) witness that Federal government have never arranged facilitation for respondents in terms of collection of tools, services and knowledge in Abuja while 46.5% (181) of the respondents witness that Federal government have arranged facilitation for respondents in terms of collection of tools, services and knowledge in Abuja.

This result shows that a less percentage of the entrepreneurs have been facilitated by the government in terms of collection of tools, services and knowledge in Abuja.

Table 30: Mentorship/Trained and Invested in Respondent's Business Setups

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES (With Private Firm)	230	59.1	59.1	59.1
	YES (With Public Firm)	88	22.6	22.6	81.7
	NO	71	18.3	18.3	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 30 shows mentorship which trained and investing in respondent's business setups. The highest respondents of 59.1% (230) had mentorship with private firms which trained and invested in their business setups while 22.6% (88) of the respondents had mentorship with public firms which trained and invested in their business set-ups.

Nevertheless, 18.3% (71) of the respondents had no mentorship which trained and invested in their business set-ups. This result shows that majority of the entrepreneurs had mentorship which trained and invested in their business setups. Therefore, they are skilled and are capable of excelling in entrepreneurship businesses.

The result is in line with assertions UBEC (2010) which said that more than 50% of average families in Abuja are skilled and that education is taken in a high premium in the area.

Challenges Affecting Business and Creating Unhealthy and Unsecured Environment for Business in Abuja

source: Field Survey May, 2025

Figure 2: Challenges affecting Business and creating unhealthy and unsecured environment for business in Abuja

Figure 2 above shows that the major challenges affecting business and creating unhealthy and unsecured environment for business operation in Abuja include, religious intolerance, incessant cases of kidnapping and insurgency of 'Boko Haram, lack of access to credit facility, power failure and multiple taxation and levies.

Logit Regression Analysis

To achieve the objectives of this study, the logit regression model specified in chapter three of the study was analysed. The results are presented as follows.

Table 31: Case Processing Summary

Unweighted Cases ^a		N	Percent
Selected Cases	Included in Analysis	389	100.0
	Missing Cases	0	.0
	Total	389	100.0
Unselected Cases		0	.0
Total		389	100.0

a. If weight is in effect, see classification table for the total number of cases.

Table 31 above shows that we are modeling 389 cases here. The SPSS default for this is listwise.

Table 32: Dependent Variable Encoding

Original Value	Internal Value
NO	0
YES	1

The Table 32 shows us that we have coded our dependent variable (Youth Employment Rate) in the right direction.

Table 33: Categorical Variables Codings

		Frequency	Parameter coding (1)
Youth Empowerment Programme	NO	167	1.000
	YES	222	.000
Youth Training	NO	107	1.000
	YES	282	.000
Technical and Vocational Education	NO	182	1.000
	YES	207	.000
Innovation Rate	NO	163	1.000
	YES	226	.000

Table 33 shows that the categorical variable for Youth Empowerment Programme, Youth Training, Technical and Vocational Education, and Innovation Rate respectively has reference category of YES. The (1) means that YEMP(1), YTRN(1), TVED(1), and INOR(1) in the results refer to NO here.

Table 34: Classification Table 1

	Observed		Predicted		
			Youth Employment Rate		Percentage Correct
			NO	YES	
Step 0	Youth Employment Rate	NO	0	191	.0
		YES	0	198	100.0
	Overall Percentage				52.2
a. Constant is included in the model.					
b. The cut value is .500					

Tables 32, 33 and 34 present the results with only the constant included before any coefficients (i.e. those relating to youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate) are entered into the equation. The Logistic regression compares this model with a model including all the predictors to determine whether the latter model is more appropriate. The Table 34 (Classification Table 1) suggests that if we have no knowledge of the youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate and guess that a youth would be employed, we would be 52.2% of the time correct.

Table 35: Constant only in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 0 Constant	.087	.049	3.223	1	.073	1.091

Table 36: Variables not in the Equation

		Score	Df	Sig.	
Step 0	Variables	YEMP(1)	31.518	1	.000
		YTRN(1)	38.434	1	.000
		TVED(1)	23.302	1	.000
		INOR(1)	52.139	1	.000
Overall Statistics		145.393	4	.000	

Table 36 (Variables not in the equation) tells us whether each of the explanatory variables (youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate) improves the model. The answer is yes for all the four variables, as they are all significant and if included would add to the predictive power of the model. If they had not been significant and able to contribute to the prediction, then termination of the analysis would obviously occur at this point.

Table 37: Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	Df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	152.467	4	.053
	Block	152.467	4	.053
	Model	152.467	4	.053

Table 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, and 43 present the results when the predictors (youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate) are included. Table 4.34 shows that we have added four variables to the model, which has collectively reduced the -2log likelihood by 152.467 with 4 degrees of freedom.

Table 38: Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	2198.235 ^a	.086	.115

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 4 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

The -2log likelihood is a measure of how well the model explains variations in the outcome of interest (Youth Employment Rate). The -2log likelihood (sometimes called, deviance) has a chi-squared distribution. The *p*-value for the result of jointly adding youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate to the model is given as 0.053 which is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05. Hence, we infer that the joint inclusion of youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate to the model is statistically insignificant. That is the predictors do not jointly exert significant effect. In other words, these explanatory variables do not jointly explain variations in the youth employment rate. That is there is no difference between the observed and model-predicted values. Thus, the model is a good fitting model.

The Cox & Snell *R*-square shows that 8.6% of the variation in the youth employment rate is being explained by the logit model. In other words, youth empowerment programme, youth

training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate contributed to approximately 9% of the variation in youth employment rate. The correlation coefficient, R , is estimated as 0.293, this implies that there is a weak positive imperfect relationship between the explained variable (youth employment rate) and the explanatory variables (youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate). The Nagelkerke R -square indicates a weak relationship of 11.5% between the predictors and the predicted.

Table 39: Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	30.361	6	.061

The Hosmer and Lemeshow goodness of fit test statistic of 0.061 which is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05 indicates that we accept the null hypothesis that there is no difference between the observed and model-predicted values, implying that the model's estimates fit the data at 5% significance level.

Table 40: Contingency Table for Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

		Youth Employment Rate = NO		Youth Employment Rate = YES		Total
		Observed	Expected	Observed	Expected	
Step 1	1	121	130.370	64	54.630	185
	2	95	96.451	52	50.549	147
	3	120	114.247	73	78.753	193
	4	75	88.868	86	72.132	161
	5	88	88.620	91	90.380	179
	6	101	88.121	93	105.879	194
	7	70	51.223	57	75.777	127
	8	70	64.958	103	108.042	173
	9	55	60.297	150	144.703	205
	10	17	28.844	117	105.156	134

Table 41: Classification Table 2

Observed			Predicted		
			Youth Employment Rate		Percentage Correct
		NO	YES		
Step 1	Youth Employment Rate		103	193	51.6
			286	196	67.7
Overall Percentage				60.0	
a. The cut value is .500					

Table 41 (Classification Table 2) shows how the classification error rate has changed from the original 52.2%. By adding the explanatory variables, we can now predict with 60% accuracy that with the knowledge of the youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate a youth would be employed. In other words, if we have knowledge of the youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate and guess that a youth would be employed, we would be 60% of the time correct. Thus, we know that the model with the predictors is a significantly

better model. The model appears relatively good, but we need to evaluate model fit and significance as well.

Table 42: Variables in the Equation

		B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 1 ^a	YEMP(1)	1.667	.108	7.127	1	.646	.749
	YTRN(1)	.153	.107	16.867	1	.000	.645
	TVED(1)	.703	.114	2.597	1	.018	.832
	INOR(1)	.247	.110	15.381	1	.242	.649
	Constant	1.144	.118	121.772	1	.000	3.693
a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: YEMP, YTRN, TVED, INOR.							

From Table 42, the deduced model is:

$$\text{logit}(Y) = 1.144 + 1.667YEMP(1) + 0.153YTRN(1) + 0.703TVED(1) + 0.247INOR(1)$$

As we have recoded youth empowerment programme to 0 = NO, 1 = YES; youth training to 0 = NO, 1 = YES; technical and vocational education to 0 = NO, 1 = YES; and innovation rate to 0 = NO, 1 = YES. This is equivalent to:

$$\text{logit}(Y) = 1.144 + 1.667YES + 0.153YES + 0.703YES + 0.247YES$$

The positive coefficient values of all the explanatory variables indicates that youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate individually have positive impact on youth employment rate. This indicates that a unit increase in youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate would bring about a respective increase in youth employment rate.

The table equally revealed that the coefficients of youth training, and technical & vocational education variables with $p = 0.000$ and $p = 0.018$ respectively are significant while the coefficients of youth empowerment programme, and innovation rate variables with $p = 0.646$ and $p = 0.242$ respectively are insignificant. In other words, youth training and technical & vocational education independently contributed significantly to youth employment rate while youth empowerment programme and innovation rate did not.

The Exp(B) column shows the relative odds (odds ratio) and indicates that youth are 0.749 times as likely to be employed than being unemployed when it has to do with youth empowerment programme, having allowed for youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate; 0.645 times as likely to be employed than being unemployed when it has to do with youth training, having allowed for youth empowerment programme, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate; 0.832 times as likely to be employed than being unemployed when it has to do with technical and vocational education, having allowed for youth empowerment programme, youth training, and innovation rate; 0.649 times as likely to to be employed than being unemployed when it has to do with innovation rate, having allowed for youth empowerment programme, youth training, and technical and vocational education.

We can thus derive an equation for the prediction of the probability of the youth employment rate as:

$$p(YER) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(1.144+1.667YEMP+0.153YTRN+0.703TVED+0.247INOR)}}$$

If all the explanatory variables are taken to be zeros (0), then

$$p(YER) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(1.144)}} \approx 0.758$$

This shows that of all the sampled respondents who did not fully engage in the youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and the innovation rate under study, approximately 76% of them would get employed.

If all the explanatory variables are taken to be one (1). That is, YEMP = YTRN = TVED = INOR = 1

$$\text{Then, } p(YER) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(1.144+1.667+0.153+0.703+0.247)}} \approx 0.977$$

This implies that of all the sampled respondents who fully engaged in the youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and the innovation rate under study, approximately 98% of them would get employed.

Table 43: Bootstrap for Variables in the Equation

		B	Bootstrap ^a				
			Bias	Std. Error	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower	Upper
Step 1	YEMP(1)	1.667	.000	.105	.006	-.491	-.079
	YTRN(1)	.153	-.004	.109	.001	-.658	-.231
	TVED(1)	.703	-.003	.118	.123	-.418	.051
	INOR(1)	.247	.002	.114	.001	-.661	-.209
	Constant	1.144	.005	.112	.001	1.096	1.531

a. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 1500 bootstrap samples

Table 44: Correlation Matrix

		Constant	YEMP(1)	YTRN(1)	TVED(1)	INOR(1)
Step 1	Constant	1.000	.340	.273	.099	.541
	YEMP(1)	.340	1.000	.080	.117	.074
	YTRN(1)	.273	.080	1.000	.043	.228
	TVED(1)	.099	.117	.043	1.000	.279
	INOR(1)	.541	.074	.228	.279	1.000

Table 44 above shows the relationship between the predictors. It is observed that there is a weak positive association among the predictors.

Summary of Results

The survey result shows the following in summary.

Opinion	Predictor Variables			
	Youth empowerment programme	Youth training	Technical and vocational education	Innovation rate
NO	167	107	182	163
YES	222	282	207	226
Parameters		Statistic		
		Estimate	Sig.	
	β_1	1.667	.646	
	β_2	.153	.000	
	β_3	.703	.018	
	β_4	.247	.242	
Test				
Omnibust Tests for Model Coefficient		Chis-square = 152.467	0.053	
-2 Log likelihood		2198.235	-	
Cox & Snell R Square		.086	-	
Multiple correlation (R)		.293	-	
Nagelkerke R Square		.115	-	
Hosmer and Lemeshow Test		Chi-square = 30.361	0.061	

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the findings is concentrated on the objectives of this study, in the order as listed in chapter one. Also, there are other relevant findings gotten from the responses of the respondents as shown in the various tables, describing the various characteristics of the variables of this study. These findings are to validate the reliability of the coefficients of the variables of the model. The broad objective of the study is to ascertain the impact of entrepreneurship development on youth employment rate in Abuja, Nigeria.

From the logit model, the coefficient value, $\beta_1 = 1.667$ implies that for every unit increase in youth empowerment programme while youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate are kept constant, we expect youth employment rate to increase by 1.667, $\beta_2 = 0.153$ implies that for every unit increase in youth training while youth empowerment programme, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate are kept constant, we expect youth employment rate to increase by 0.153, $\beta_3 = 0.703$ implies that for every unit increase in technical and vocational education while youth empowerment programme, youth training, and innovation rate are kept constant, we expect youth employment rate to increase by 0.703, $\beta_4 = 0.247$ implies that for every unit increase in innovation rate while youth empowerment programme, youth training, and technical and vocational education are kept constant, we expect youth employment rate to increase by 0.247. The positive coefficient values of all the explanatory variables indicates that youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate individually have positive impact on youth employment rate. In other words, entrepreneurship development effectively impacted youth employment rate in Abuja.

These findings are in line with Gambo et al. (2025). Their research on the relationship between entrepreneurship and employment often highlights how entrepreneurship impacts job creation and economic growth. Their work suggests that while entrepreneurship can lead to increased

employment, the effect may vary based on regional factors and the nature of government support and with findings of William J. Baumol’s work on entrepreneurship and economic development discusses how entrepreneurship can contribute to economic growth and job creation, albeit with varying levels of effectiveness depending on the support structures and economic environment.

The prior test is summarized in the table below.

Variable	Expected sign	Obtained signs	Conclusion
YEMP	Positive (+)	Positive (+)	Conform
YTRN	Positive (+)	Positive (+)	Conform
TVED	Positive (+)	Positive (+)	Conform
INOR	Positive (+)	Positive (+)	Conform

Source: Field Survey (2025)

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study examined the impact of entrepreneurship development on youth employment rate in Abuja, Nigeria. Methodologically, the study used primary data collected through structured surveys. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics and logit regression. The first objective of the study sought to ascertain the impact and significance of youth empowerment programme on youth employment rate. The result from the analysis revealed that youth empowerment programme has a positive but insignificant impact on youth employment rate in Abuja. The second objective aim to determine the influence and significance of youth training on youth employment rate. The result showed that youth training has a positive significant influence on youth employment rate in Abuja. The third objective aim to analyze the effect and significance of technical and vocational education on youth employment rate. The result revealed that technical and vocational education has a positive significant effect on youth employment rate in Abuja. The fourth objective sought to investigate the significant relationship between innovation rate and youth employment rate. The result showed that innovation rate has a positive but insignificant effect on youth employment rate in Abuja. The fifth objective aim to assess the joint significant effect of youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate on youth employment rate. The result revealed that youth empowerment programme, youth training, technical and vocational education, and innovation rate do not jointly exert significant impact on youth employment rate in Abuja.

Recommendations

Given the conclusions drawn from this study, some recommendations are presented in this section which will help to promote entrepreneurship development for youth employment in Abuja, Nigeria at large.

- i. Easy access to entrepreneurial services to potential and already entrepreneurs should be promoted by setting up macroeconomics policies such as judiciary to prosecute corrupt government officials whose aims and goal is to loot the treasury of entrepreneurship schemes and wreck the entrepreneurship training and skills acquisition centres.

- ii. Entrepreneurship programme should only be run by entrepreneurs or entrepreneurship instructors in each kind or field of entrepreneurship to avoid wrong teaching and implementation and more entrepreneurship programs should be administered and in appropriate content with what is needed and to the right set of people. Also, entrepreneurship programs should be presented more in the rural areas to enable a proper dissemination to the programs.
- iii. To promote entrepreneurship effectively, the Nigerian government should set up a policy strategy to embark on feedback mission on entrepreneurship through studying the entrepreneurship dynamism and its ecosystem. This can be done through the study on entrepreneurship and the network evolution of the main actors; the individual entrepreneurs, the government or the state men who regulate and control the affairs of entrepreneurship to prevent inappropriate policy interventions.
- iv. Issues responsible for low entrepreneurship productivity that led to poverty in the region also, are political insecurity, social evil such as terrorism, insurgencies, communal and inter-religious conflicts. These issues are security threat to business progress. Thus, as part of macroeconomic policy to guide economic activities, region security agency should be instituted by the Nigerian government. This will combat the business insecurity in the region

References

- 1) Adebayo, A. (2022). Youth employment and National Directorate of Employment self-employment programme. *Nigerian Journal of Economics and Social Studies* 4(1).
- 2) Ako, P.J. (2018). Education and national development in Nigeria: Implications for counseling, *International and National Development in Nigeria: Implication for Counseling*, 6(1), 77-86
- 3) Alabi, T. & Salami, U. J. (2022). Factors associated with entrepreneurship development among graduates in Abuja Municipal Area Council, *Lapai International Journal Of Management And Social Sciences*, 14(1), 111-119
- 4) Balogun, B. B. & Marafa, A. I (2022). The effect of entrepreneurship development on employment generation in some selected rural areas of kebbi state, *International Journal for Research Trends and Innovation*, 7(11), 220-224
- 5) Baumol, W.J. (1990). Entrepreneurship: Productive, unproductive and destructive. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98 (5), 893-921.
- 6) Baumol, W.J. (1993). Formal entrepreneurship theory in economics: Existence and bones. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 8(3), 197–210.
- 7) Bonito, J. D., Daantos, F. J., Mateo, J. C., & Rosete, M. A. (2017). Do entrepreneurship and economic growth affect poverty, income inequality and economic development? *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 6(1), 33-43.
- 8) Desai, S. (2017). Measuring entrepreneurship: Type, motivation, and growth. Evidence-base policy making *I Z A World Labour*. 1-2 wol.iza.org.
- 9) Drucker, P. F. (2007). *Management challenges for the 21st century*. Harper Business.

- 10) Gambo, A. A., Akpan, M., Ogwuche, D. & Umeokwobi, R. (2025). Effect of entrepreneurship development on employment generation in Nigeria: A case study of Nasarawa State, *Financial Economics Letters*, 4(1), 15-30
- 11) Kim, A., Song, Y., Kim, M., Lee, K., & Cheon, J. H. (2018). Logistic regression model training based on the approximate homomorphic encryption. *BMC medical genomics*, 11(4), 83. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12920-018-0401-7>
- 12) Lambo, N., (2022). Entrepreneurship and Employment: Regions in focus? Regional Studies Association International Conference Gateway 12: Renegotiating Peripheries Lisbon, Portugal April 2-5.
- 13) Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). *Employment*. In Merriam-Webster.com dictionary. Retrieved August 12, 2024, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/employment>
- 14) Misango, S.B., & Ongiti, O. (2013). Do women entrepreneurs play a role in reducing poverty? A case in Kenya. *International review of management and Business Research*, 2, 1-8.
- 15) Musa, U. M., Abdullah, M.A., & Wahid, R. (2016). Politics of poverty alleviation programs in Nigeria: Challenges and prospect. *Journal of Education and Social Science*, 4, 311-316.
- 16) National Bureau of statistics (NBS) (2015). Poverty survey. <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/download/486>.
- 17) National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2016). Unemployment rate. <https://www.google.com>
- 18) National Population Commission [NPC] (2006). The 2006 report. Abuja. <https://www.google.com>
- 19) Oni O. (2022). Labour market adjustments and Employment Issue in Nigeria. In: *Unemployment and Underemployment in Nigeria*. Annual conference proceedings of the Nigerian Economic Society, Kaduna.
- 20) Parker J, (2022). Literature review on social entrepreneurship and Employment Generation. Canadian Centre for Social Entrepreneurship November 2000.
- 21) Schumpeter, J. A. (1934). *The theory of economic development: An inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest and the business cycle*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- 22) World Bank. (2018). *Glossary of employment terms*. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/employment>